

Vibrational Analysis of Glyoxal-h₂-d₂ and hd

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A complete vibrational analysis has been made for glyoxal-h₂, -d₂ and hd. A reasonable set of force constants has been obtained using the general valence force field by the Wilson's F-G matrix method. Using these values other important molecular constants such as mean amplitudes of vibration, generalised mean-square amplitudes of vibration, shrinkage constants, Coriolis coupling constants, centrifugal distortion constants and thermodynamic properties have been computed and presented. A comparison is made between the values obtained in the present investigation and the values available in literature.

TRAMER and co-workers¹ recorded gas phase emission spectra of glyoxal-h₂ and -d₂, presenting in the case of the deuterated species some weak bands not reported earlier. From the frequency of combination bands of the ir spectrum of these molecules by Cole and Osborne², several bands can be assigned. Cossart-Magos³ has made the normal coordinate analysis of these molecules on the basis of valence force field. A previous calculation⁴ of the fundamental frequencies of glyoxal-h₂ and -d₂ used a modified Urey-Bradley force field. Cossart-Magos³ has introduced two more interaction constants which were absent in the Urey-Bradley force field. The structural parameters used for the present investigation have been taken from the work of Kuchitsu *et al*⁵ conjugating electron diffraction and spectroscopic data. The normal modes of vibration are distributed among the two symmetry species as 5A_g+4B_u. However, potential energy constants have been reinvestigated using the general valence force field. On the basis of GVFF, the mean square amplitudes of vibration, the generalised mean square amplitudes of vibration, shrinkage constants, Coriolis coupling constants, centrifugal distortion constants and thermodynamic quantities have been computed for these molecules.

The molecular configuration, numbering of atoms and the orientation of the Cartesian coordinate axes are shown in Fig. 1.

Methods of calculation :

The potential energy matrix F has been derived relating to the general valence force field. The kinetic energy matrix G has been obtained by making use of the geometrical parameters according to the relation $G=BM^{-1}B'$, where M^{-1} is a diagonal matrix of the reciprocal masses and B is the transformation matrix from Cartesian displacement coordinates to internal coordinates. By solving the

Fig. 1. The molecular configuration, numbering of atoms and the orientation of the Cartesian coordinate axes of glyoxal-h₂, -d₂ and hd.

secular equation⁶ $|FG-E\lambda| = 0$, a reasonable set of force constants has been evaluated.

The symmetrised mean square amplitude matrix Σ has been calculated by L-matrix method⁷. The generalised mean square amplitudes $\langle(\Delta z)^2\rangle$, $\langle(\Delta y)^2\rangle$ and $\langle(\Delta x)^2\rangle$ have been computed by deriving relevant expressions following the method of Morino and Hirota⁸. The shrinkage constants have been determined from the perpendicular mean square amplitudes by the method suggested by Morino *et al*⁹.

Applying Jahn's rule¹⁰, the non-vanishing zeta values are found to be of the type ζ^z arising from the coupling $A_x \times A_x$ and $B_u \times B_u$. These constants have been estimated using the matrix relation,

$$\zeta^\alpha = L^{-1}C^\alpha \bar{L}^{-1}$$

where L is the normal coordinate transformation matrix and C^α ($\alpha=x, y, z$) is the skew symmetric matrix obtained by the vector method of Meal and Polo¹¹.

Since the bonds between the atoms in a molecule are not rigid, the interatomic distances will vary

with the speed of rotation giving rise to centrifugal distortion. The centrifugal distortion constants have been computed with the aid of the relations given by Kivelson and Wilson¹² and by Cyvin *et al*¹³.

Results and Discussion

The internal force constants obtained using GVFF are presented in Table 1 along with the

TABLE 1—THE INTERNAL FORCE CONSTANTS OF GLYOXAL AND ITS ISOTOPES

Designation	(m.dyne/Å)	
	values	values from Ref. (3)
f_r	4.390	4.396
f_d	12.625	12.663
f_R	4.700	4.700
f_{rr}	0.010	
f_{dd}	-0.175	
f_β	0.533	0.548
$f_{\beta\beta}$	-0.013	
f_α	0.472	0.551
$f_{\alpha\alpha}$	-0.013	
$f_{d\beta}$	-0.495	
$f_{d\alpha}$	0.309	
f_R	-0.094	-0.123
$f_{R\alpha}$	0.260	0.884

values calculated by Cossart-Magos⁸ for comparison. The agreement is found to be quite satisfactory. The force constant f_r is found to be about three times the force constant f_d . Also the force constant f_α is smaller than f_β . It has been shown by Ohwada¹⁴ that the interaction force constant of highly delocalised bond molecule tends to take a large +ve value while that of highly localised bond molecule, a -ve value. Hence the sign of the force constant is a measure of the electron localization or delocalization in a molecule. The values evaluated in the present investigation are made use of for the calculation of other molecular constants.

The mean square amplitude quantities calculated at 300 K are given in Table 2. The generalised mean square amplitudes of vibration and the shrinkage constants are listed in Table 3. The

TABLE 2—MEAN-SQUARE AMPLITUDES OF VIBRATION OF GLYOXAL AND ITS ISOTOPES AT 300 K (Å²) × 10⁻⁴

Designation	C ₂ H ₂ O ₂	C ₂ D ₂ O ₂	C ₂ HDO ₂
σ_r	69.201	54.958	66.610
σ_d	14.479	21.672	17.687
σ_R	25.836	29.037	25.617
σ_β	111.370	75.878	102.810
σ_α	55.399	67.458	45.076
σ_{rr}	-1.682	4.967	25.770
σ_{dd}	0.340	-2.119	-0.590
$\sigma_{\alpha\alpha}$	16.340	22.195	1.770
$\sigma_{\beta\beta}$	-29.818	11.197	32.859
$\sigma_{r\alpha}$	-1.180	-5.500	-7.370
σ_r	4.360	-10.004	-14.143
σ_{Rr}	-2.170	-4.780	-1.900
σ_{rd}	2.850	26.540	-3.480
$\sigma_{d\beta}$	7.260	8.760	9.880
σ_{Rd}	-5.990	-4.960	-5.810
$\sigma_{d\alpha}$	-4.830	-15.380	-2.870
$\sigma_{R\alpha}$	-7.260	-6.630	-4.900
$\sigma_{\beta\alpha}$	-4.100	-25.801	-13.583
σ_R	-9.760	-5.590	-9.080

parallel mean square amplitudes $\langle(\Delta z)^2\rangle$ compare very well with the mean square amplitude quantities (σ). Since $f_r \langle f_d, \sigma_r \rangle \sigma_d$. It can also be seen that since f_d is very large, the mean square amplitude σ_d is found to be very small. Also the natural and practical shrinkages are found to be equal.

The Coriolis coupling coefficients are presented in Table 4. These coefficients facilitate the analysis of vibration-rotation spectra. The following zeta square sum rule is found to be satisfied for the $A_g \times A_g$ coupling :

$$\zeta_{1,2}^2 + \zeta_{1,3}^2 + \zeta_{1,4}^2 + \zeta_{1,5}^2 = 1$$

The centrifugal distortion constants are listed in Table 5. As there is no experimental data available

TABLE 3—GENERALISED MEAN-SQUARE AMPLITUDES OF VIBRATION (Å²) × 10⁻⁴ AND SHRINKAGE CONSTANTS (Å)

Atom pair	Designation	C ₂ H ₂ O ₂	C ₂ D ₂ O ₂	C ₂ HDO ₂	Shrinkage constants
G-O	$\langle(\Delta z)^2\rangle$	14.471	21.414	17.720	
	$\langle(\Delta y)^2\rangle$	59.248	66.828	62.437	
	$\langle(\Delta z \Delta y)\rangle$	0.616	-9.700	2.683	
G-H	$\langle(\Delta z)^2\rangle$	69.109	54.960	66.010	
	$\langle(\Delta y)^2\rangle$	240.180	140.070	170.568	
	$\langle(\Delta z \Delta y)\rangle$	-8.879	-4.336	6.438	
G-C	$\langle(\Delta z)^2\rangle$	25.830	29.037	25.617	
	$\langle(\Delta y)^2\rangle$	107.891	97.638	102.814	
	$\langle(\Delta z \Delta y)\rangle$	-0.494	-4.213	-6.124	
G...H	$\langle(\Delta z)^2\rangle$	52.429	26.138	64.899	
	$\langle(\Delta y)^2\rangle$	145.284	90.005	167.778	
	$\langle(\Delta z \Delta y)\rangle$	64.702	50.856	110.872	
G...O	$\langle(\Delta z)^2\rangle$	22.627	20.078	23.884	
	$\langle(\Delta y)^2\rangle$	36.186	55.467	28.742	
	$\langle(\Delta z \Delta y)\rangle$	17.854	21.629	11.389	

$$\delta C_2 \dots O_2 = -0.04039 - 0.04565 - 0.03591$$

$$\delta O_2 \dots H_2 = -0.03073 - 0.03588 - 0.03626$$

TABLE 4—CORIOLIS COUPLING CONSTANTS OF GLYOXAL AND ITS ISOTOPES

Designation	Coupling A _g × A _g		
	C ₂ H ₂ O ₂	C ₂ D ₂ O ₂	C ₂ HDO ₂
ζ_{13}^z	0.22978	0.26674	0.26478
ζ_{13}^x	0.92950	0.74499	0.72619
ζ_{14}^z	-0.00470	-0.09529	0.04325
ζ_{15}^z	0.28923	0.60438	0.63350
ζ_{23}^z	-0.02583	0.30994	-0.17937
ζ_{24}^z	0.69161	0.59106	0.83205
ζ_{25}^z	-0.25844	-0.34665	-0.31335
ζ_{34}^z	0.05024	0.27566	0.11695
ζ_{35}^z	0.16566	0.22569	0.53959
ζ_{45}^z	0.66714	0.55609	0.43699
	Coupling B _u × B _u		
ζ_{67}^z	0.16286	0.24054	0.29526
ζ_{68}^z	0.96171	0.97132	0.95413
ζ_{69}^z	-0.30432	0.02406	-0.04679
ζ_{78}^z	-0.64662	0.02416	-0.04874
ζ_{79}^z	-0.93848	-0.97041	-0.97074
ζ_{89}^z	0.16473	0.24003	0.29764

for centrifugal distortion constants, no comparison could be attempted.

TABLE 5—CENTRIFUGAL STRETCHING COEFFICIENTS (M Hz) OF GLYOXAL AND ITS ISOTOPES

	C ₂ H ₂ O ₂	C ₂ D ₂ O ₂	C ₂ HDO ₂
D _J	0.021006	0.018905	0.019379
D _K	0.023445	0.021074	0.021620
D _{JK}	-0.043366	-0.039030	-0.039978
R _a	-0.004201	-0.003795	-0.003930
R _b	-0.002033	-0.001355	-0.001559
δ _J	-0.011451	-0.010638	-0.010706

Tables 6-8 give the values of the heat capacity, free energy, heat content, and entropy computed from the observed vibrational frequency data, over

TABLE 6—THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS OF C₂H₂O₂

T(K)	S	F	C _p	H
100	52.27162	44.28551	8.15252	7.98611
200	58.15651	49.89556	8.92176	8.26095
273	61.01304	52.50282	9.46042	8.51022
300	61.91487	53.31010	9.66482	8.60478
400	64.79958	55.83403	10.44552	8.96550
500	67.21454	57.87513	11.21869	9.33941
600	69.32876	59.61370	11.93254	9.71506
700	71.20327	61.18487	12.54130	10.06840
800	72.92414	62.50314	13.10920	10.42100
900	74.50392	63.75563	13.58370	10.74820
1000	75.96335	64.90725	13.99180	11.05610

TABLE 7—THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS OF C₂D₂O₂

T(K)	S	F	C _p	H
100	52.52730	44.52650	8.20558	8.00080
200	58.46950	50.15779	9.05582	8.31176
273	61.38428	52.78565	9.72457	8.59863
300	62.31166	53.60235	9.96853	8.70931
400	65.30819	56.16677	10.88919	9.14141
500	67.83095	58.25348	11.75101	9.57747
600	70.02051	60.01901	12.53400	10.00150
700	72.02529	61.61139	13.18480	10.41390
800	73.82231	63.02656	13.74195	10.79580
900	75.46160	64.31400	14.21030	11.14760
1000	76.98467	65.50957	14.58600	11.47510

TABLE 8—THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS OF C₂HDO₂

T(K)	S	F	C _p	H
100	53.78674	45.79274	8.18181	7.99400
200	59.70412	51.41496	8.99163	8.28915
273	62.58837	54.03270	9.58574	8.55567
300	63.50303	54.84456	9.81322	8.65847
400	66.44200	57.39019	10.66200	9.05401
500	68.91183	59.45503	11.47710	9.45680
600	70.62565	60.99957	12.00542	9.62608
700	73.00495	62.76175	12.87090	10.24320'
800	74.76152	64.15462	13.42370	10.60690
900	76.37686	65.42686	13.89520	10.95000
1000	77.89043	66.59183	14.28710	11.29860

the range 100-1000K at intervals of 100K. The calculations are all based on a rigid rotor harmonic oscillator model with no interaction between the vibrational and rotational energies. The quantities evaluated are the combined translational rotational and vibrational contributions.

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